

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Potential of organic soil amendments derived from side streams of forest industry in early potato fields must be investigated further

Since the growing period of early potato in Finland is short, only 1.5-2 months, the soil remains bare for most of the year, making it prone to erosion. Therefore, early potato farmers would benefit from management practices that could prevent nutrient and carbon loss, as well as further damage. Earlier results have shown promising positive effects of organic amendments processed from the side-streams of the forestry and pulp industry on soil structure and microbiology. Therefore, field case study experiment was carried out in early potato field in the boreal pedoclimatic region in Finland, where the potential beneficial effect of three different fibre sludges as soil amendments were investigated for 3 years: nutrient-poor fiber sludge (FB, also referred to as “zero fiber”), and two nutrient-rich sludges, composted pulp mill sludge (CPMS) and lime-stabilised

pulp mill sludge (LPMS). Based on the results the use of side-stream based forest-derived recycled organic soil amendments in boreal early potato field cannot be directly recommended, since they produced extra costs for farmers because of the decreased gross-margins. The impacts of these amendments in boreal early potato fields on soil were neutral; thus, their use does not cause harm to soil biology. Although short-term effects on soil function or biology could not be detected, long-term benefits may be observed, therefore further research in this field is recommended. However, potential of organic side-streams as soil amendments to complement fertilizers to support circular economy, and the overall national security of supply should be investigated more.

1. Zero fiber as organic soil amendment originating from the Finnish pulp mill spread into the boreal field.

KEYWORDS

Soil amendment, side streams of industry, early potato

AUTHORSHIP

Krista Peltoniemi, Natural Resources Institution Finland (Luke), Finland

Eija Pouta Natural Resources Institution Finland (Luke), Finland,
Sari Iivonen, Finnish Organic Research Institute/Luke, Finland

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